

Cost of Not Investing (CONI) in Intelligent Processes Automation Survey

Background

The aim of this survey is to measure and evaluate the understanding of costs and implications of delayed investment in process automation. Your responses will help develop a comprehensive understanding of how organizations evaluate and experience the costs of delayed automation investment.

Confidentiality Statement

All responses will be treated confidentially and used solely for academic research purposes, in line with LUT data processing policy: <https://www.lut.fi/en/data-protection>. The results will be reported only in an anonymized and aggregate form, ensuring no individual organization can be identified.

Part 1: Organizational Context

Q1. What industry sector best describes your organization?

- Manufacturing
- Financial Services
- Healthcare
- Retail/E-commerce
- Technology
- Logistics/Supply Chain
- Professional Services
- Other (please specify):

Q2. How many employees does your organization have?

- 1-50
- 51-250
- 251-1000
- 1001-5000
- 5000+

Q3. What was your organization's annual revenue in the last fiscal year?

- Less than \$1 million
- \$1-10 million
- \$11-50 million
- \$51-250 million
- \$251-1000 million
- Over \$1 billion
- Prefer not to say

Q4. What is your role in the organization?

- C-level executive
- Senior management
- Middle management
- Technical specialist
- Process owner
- Other (please specify):

Q5. Years of experience in current role:

- Less than 1 year
- 1-3 years
- 4-7 years
- 8-12 years
- 12+ years

Q6. How would you rate your familiarity with automation technologies?

- 1 = Basic awareness
- 2 = Working knowledge
- 3 = Expert understanding

Part 2: Current Automation Status

Q7. How would you rate your organization's current level of process automation?

- 1 = Mostly manual processes
- 2 = Basic automation of simple tasks
- 3 = Partial automation of complex processes
- 4 = Extensive automation across multiple areas
- 5 = Full automation with AI/ML capabilities

Q8. Which of the following processes are currently automated in your organization? (Select all that apply)

- Customer service
- Financial processes
- Human resources
- Supply chain management
- Production/Operations
- Data analysis
- Quality control
- Other (please specify)

Q9. According to your understanding, what percentage of your core business processes are currently automated?

Q10. When was your last investment in process automation software?

- Within the last 6 months
- 6-12 months ago
- 1-2 years ago
- 2-5 years ago
- More than 5 years ago
- Never

Q11. As far as you are aware, kind of technologies are used for automating processes your work?

Part 3: CONI Perception

For the following statements, please indicate your level of agreement:

- Strongly Disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neutral (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly Agree (5)

Q12. Operational Impact

- "Delaying automation investments increases our operational costs"
- "Our efficiency gap with competitors grows larger as we delay automation"
- "Manual processes are becoming increasingly expensive to maintain"
- "We are losing market opportunities due to slower process execution"
- "Our service quality suffers from lack of automation"
- "Our response times to market changes suffer due to delayed automation investments."
- "Delays in automation cause increased downtime and disruptions in our business processes."

Q13. Strategic Impact

- "Competitors with higher automation levels are gaining market share"
- "We are missing opportunities for data-driven decision making"
- "Our innovation capability is limited by manual processes"
- "Customer satisfaction is negatively affected by our automation level"
- "We struggle to scale our operations efficiently"
- "Delayed investments in automation limit our strategic flexibility and ability to react to competitors' moves."
- "We risk losing first-mover advantages by not promptly automating key processes."

Q14. Human Capital Impact

- "We have difficulty attracting talented employees due to outdated processes"
- "Employee satisfaction is lower due to manual, repetitive tasks"
- "Staff turnover is higher in areas with low automation"
- "Training costs are increasing due to complex manual processes"
- "Workforce productivity is limited by lack of automation"
- "Employees' innovation potential is underutilized due to the burden of repetitive manual tasks."
- "Our failure to automate causes valuable employees to leave for competitors with better automation."

Q15. How does your organization evaluate automation investment decisions? (Select all that apply)

- Traditional ROI analysis
- Cost-benefit analysis
- Competitive analysis
- Strategic necessity evaluation
- Total Cost of Ownership (TCO)
- Risk assessment
- Other (please specify)
- I do not know

Q16. What factors are considered when calculating the cost of not automating? (Select all that apply)

- Operational inefficiencies
- Labor costs
- Error rates
- Customer satisfaction
- Market share loss
- Employee satisfaction
- Competitive disadvantage
- Other (please specify)
- I do not know

Q17. How do you measure or estimate these costs?

For the following barriers, please indicate the level of significance:

- Not Significant (1)
- Slightly Significant (2)
- Moderately Significant (3)
- Very Significant (4)
- Extremely Significant (5)

Q18. Rate the significance of these barriers to automation implementation:

- Initial investment costs
- Implementation complexity
- Employee resistance
- Legacy system integration
- Lack of expertise
- Uncertain ROI
- Resource constraints
- Organizational culture
- Security concerns
- Regulatory compliance

Q19. What is your automation investment timeline?

- Within 6 months
- 6-12 months
- 1-2 years
- 2+ years
- No current plans
- I don't know

Q20. Which processes are your top priorities for automation? (Select up to 3)

Q21. What percentage of your operations do you plan to automate in the next 2 years?

Part 4: CONI Awareness

Q22. How often does your organization explicitly consider the strategic and hidden costs (e.g., competitive risks, lost opportunities, reduced agility) of not investing when making automation decisions?

- Never (e.g., (we only focus on immediate direct costs/benefits))
- Rarely (e.g., we occasionally recognize, but do not systematically analyse these costs)
- Sometimes (e.g. consideration occurs, but inconsistently or informally)
- Often (e.g., regularly considered as part of strategic decision-making)
- Always (e.g., systematic and formal consideration during all investment decision-making)

Q23. Do you have a formal method for evaluating the cost of delayed automation?

- Yes, fully established and systematically applied (please describe)
- Partially established or under development
- No formal approach, evaluation is informal or intuitive
- No consideration at all

Q24. What would help your organization better evaluate the cost of not investing in automation? (Select all that apply)

- Better measurement tools
- Industry benchmarks or comparative data
- Case studies
- ROI calculators
- External consulting or expert consultation
- Specialized training or education
- Other (please specify)